

Melu doors

Solid wooden doors using recovered wood

Wood materials are recovered from old doors and old wooden constructions to be reused as core for new, custom-made solid wooden doors with a unique design. The product portfolio includes also specialized folding doors, sliding doors, windbreaks and wall coverings.

Highlights of innovative features

- Solid doors are unique manufactured pieces for customers who value natural materials, strength and beauty in their homes.
- Custom-made design achieves high quality products with a long lifetime and valorizes the natural material wood.

Recovered wood material valorization in high-end products gives them a second life, as they would otherwise be considered waste. They substitute non-renewable materials and prolong the carbon storage impact of these products. Use of recycled materials in customized products helps to raise awareness for Circular Economy among end users.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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